

Triterpenes from *Careya arborea* : Structure of Careyagenol D*

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From chemical and physico-chemical studies, the structure of careyagenol D isolated from the acid hydrolyzate of the saponin of seeds of *Careya arborea* has been established as olean-12, 15-diene, -3 β , 21 α , 22 α , 28-tetrol (Ia). Besides this, three other polyhydroxy triterpenoid sapogenols characterised as barringtonol C, barringtonol D and 16-desoxy barringtonol C have also been isolated.

CHAKRABORTI and Barua¹ reported the complete structure of barringtonol D (IIa) isolated from *Barringtonia acutangula* (N.O. Lecythidaceae). On treatment with *p*-toluene sulphonic acid or hydrogen chloride, a tetrol was reported to have been obtained from barringtonol D whose structure was not worked out. Thomson² while reporting the structure of isoescigenin suggested from an analogy with isoescigenin that the tetrol mentioned above might have the structure (III) without any experimental evidence.

The present communication deals with the isolation and structure elucidation of the above mentioned tetrol, named careyagenol D along with a number of related triterpene alcohols from the seeds of *Careya arborea* (N.O. Lecythidaceae). Preliminary chemical investigations have already been done on the leaves³, stem bark⁴ and the seeds⁵⁻⁷ of the plant.

On acid hydrolysis of the crude saponin obtained from the seeds and subsequent chromatography over alumina, four sapogenols have so far been obtained, tentatively designated as careyagenol A, B, C, D according to the increasing order of their R_f values. The best separation was eventually carried out from the mixture of the sapogenol acetates whereby careyagenol D acetate was easily separated owing to its low solubility in methanol, whereas the other acetates were found to be comparatively more soluble in this solvent.

Careyagenol D :

Careyagenol D (Ia), C₃₀H₄₈O₄, m.p. 301-2°, [α]_D²⁵ +15.5° (ethanol) on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine afforded the tetraacetate (Ib), C₃₈H₅₆O₈, m.p. 282-83°, [α]_D²⁵ -8° (CHCl₃). The tetraacetate had no free hydroxyl as revealed by its IR spectrum (Nujol). Formation of the tetraacetate suggests that the four oxygen atoms in careyagenol D are present as hydroxyl functions. Further, the compound shows violet to pink colouration in the Liebermann-Burchard test indicating it to be a triterpene.

Molecular formula, formation of tetraacetate, positive Liebermann-Burchard test coupled with mass and NMR spectra suggested that careyagenol D is a pentacyclic triterpene having two double bonds and four hydroxyl groups. Neither of the two double bonds, however, could be hydrogenated even under forcing conditions. The mass fragmentation pattern of the tetraacetate (Ib) is typical of Δ^{12} -oleanene or Δ^{12} -ursene type of triterpenes⁸. Presence of 12:13 double bond was further supported by the formation of α , β -unsaturated ketone (IV) when careyagenol D tetraacetate was treated with CrO₃ in glacial acetic acid. The unsaturated ketone (IV) shows, however, lower UV absorption maximum (238 nm, log ϵ 4.11) than is usually observed for 11-keto Δ^{12} - β amyrins. Moreover, the mass fragmentation pattern of the tetraacetate is indicative of the fact that one of the four hydroxyl groups of careyagenol D is present in the part containing rings A/B and the other three hydroxyl groups in addition to the second double bond are present in the part containing rings C/D/E. The NMR data of (Ib) (Table 1) discloses the existence of seven tertiary methyls (eliminating the possibility of Δ^{12} -ursene skeleton), three olefinic hydrogens and four acetoxy functions, among which one is attached to primary and the other three are connected to secondary hydroxyls.

That the primary hydroxyl is attached to C₂₈ is suggested by the pronounced loss of 73 mass unit both from the molecular ion of (Ib) as well as from the retro-Diels-Alder fragment *b*. The presence of a secondary hydroxyl group at C₃ is more probable from biogenetic ground. Moreover, its equatorial (β) orientation is supported by the presence of a triplet-like multiplet (1H) centered at δ 4.6 in the NMR spectrum of (Ib) with splitting pattern characteristic of the proton alpha to the 3 β acetoxy group^{9,10}. The tetraacetate (Ib) however, did not form the expected $\Delta^{11:12, 13:18}$ -heteroannular diene typical of Δ^{12} -oleanenes when heated with SeO₂ in glacial acetic acid¹¹.

The evidences adduced so far suggested that careyagenol D is a tetrahydroxy Δ^{12} -oleanene with an additional disubstituted double bond. After ascertaining

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TABLE I. NMR DATA OF CAREYAGENOL D TETRAACETATE AT 100 MHz GIVEN IN δ VALUES

Tertiary methyls	-OCOCH ₃	C ₁₇ -CH ₂ OAc	C-3 α H	C-12H	C-21H C-22H	C-15H C-16H
0.82(3H,s)	2.0 (3H,s)	3.86(2H,s)	4.55	5.40	4.99	5.51
0.85(3H,s)	2.10(9H,s)		(1H,t-like)	(1H,m)	5.38	5.71
0.90(3H,s)					(ABq,J=3Hz)	(ABq,J=10Hz)
0.93(3H,s)						
0.98(3H,s)						
1.12(3H,s)						
1.31(3H,s)						

s = Singlet, m = Multiplet, q = Quartet, t = Triplet.

the position of a secondary hydroxyl at C₃ and the primary hydroxyl at C₂₈ the positions of the other two hydroxyls as well as the disubstituted double bond remain to be assigned. Careyagenol D or its acetate was found to be transparent to UV above 208 nm eliminating thereby the possibility of the presence of any kind of conjugated system. Further, the tetrol (Ia) consumes one mole of periodic acid indicating the presence of a α -glycol system. The rate of consumption of lead tetraacetate was found to be inconclusive with regard to ascertaining either *cis* or *trans* orientation of the α -glycol. However, the α -glycol system may be placed at C₁₅ and C₁₆ and the disubstituted double bond at 21:22 or *vice versa*. But the hydroxyl at C₁₅ whether axial or equatorial is known to be highly hindered¹² where as C₁₆-axial hydroxyl has also been shown to be hindered. The ease of formation of the tetraacetate (Ib) at room temperature annuls the probability of the α -glycol system being present at C₁₅ and C₁₆. In consequence, the presence of the α -glycol system at C₂₁ and C₂₂ and that of the disubstituted double bond at 15:16 seems to be more probable. The highly hindered nature of the 15:16 disubstituted

double bond is understandable due to steric hindrance by the neighbouring groups of the molecule as has been mentioned by Thomson in case of isoescigenin². As regards the orientations of C₂₁ and C₂₂ hydroxyls the NMR spectrum of the tetraacetate (Ib) was quite informative. The spectrum shows a pair of doublets centered at δ 5.01 ($J = 3$ Hz) and δ 5.38 ($J = 3$ Hz) due to the two vicinal hydrogens at C₂₁ and C₂₂. The low coupling constant (3 Hz) indicates that the two vicinal hydrogens are either in diequatorial or axial-equatorial relationship. Consequently, the NMR data alone is not conclusive in determining the orientations of the two vicinal hydroxyls.

It is interesting to note that it was possible to prepare two isomeric acetonides from careyagenol D. If the two vicinal hydroxyls were in diequatorial orientation (i.e. *trans*) then acetonide formation by a *trans* α -glycol system being unlikely, only one acetonide involving C₂₁ and C₂₈ hydroxyls could be possible. Hence, it follows that the hydroxyls at C₂₁ and C₂₂ lie in the axial-equatorial orientation. As which of the two hydroxyls is equatorial or axial

was revealed by conversion of barringtogenol D (also isolated from the same source) to careyagenol D by the action of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid on the triacetate of the former with acetic anhydride and subsequent saponification of the product. Equatorial orientation of the C₂₂-OH in barringtogenol D, barringtogenol C, aescigenin, isoescigenin etc. has been proved beyond doubt by Kitagawa *et al*¹³⁻¹⁴ and supported by Barua *et al*¹⁵, Tschesche *et al*^{16,17} and finally by Hoppe *et al*¹⁸ by X-ray crystallography. Therefore, it is concluded that in careyagenol D, C₂₁-OH is axial (α) and C₂₂-OH is equatorial (α) and the structure is best represented as (Ia).

The mass spectrum of careyagenol D tetraacetate (Ib) is in complete agreement with the assigned structure and shows typical retro-Diels-Alder fragmentation pattern expected of olean-12-enes.

Careyagenol C (Barringtogenol D) :

Careyagenol C (IIa), C₃₀H₄₈O₄, m.p. 308-10°, [α]_D²⁰ +20.4° (EtOH), formed a triacetate (IIb), C₃₆H₅₄O₇, m.p. 237°-38°, M⁺ 598, [α]_D²⁰ +78° (CHCl₃) and a diketomethylester, C₃₁H₄₄O₅, m.p. 220°-21°, M⁺ 496. The compound (IIa) was eventually found to be identical with barringtogenol D¹. The NMR spectrum (60 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS) of the triacetate (IIb) shows down field signals at δ 5.31 (1H at C₂₂ s), 5.31 (a vinyl proton at C₁₂, m), 4.58 (1H, C-3 α H, *t*-like), 4.08 (2H at C₂₃, q, J = 11 Hz), 3.66 (1H at C₂₁, s) and 2.08 (9H, 3x-OCOCH₃, s). The seven tertiary methyls appear at δ 0.91 (9H, s), 0.98 (3H, s), 1.10 (3H, s), 1.15 (3H, s) and 1.54 (3H, s). The down field methyl signal at δ 1.54 is assigned to the C-27 methyl and this down-field shift is attributed to the deshielding effect of the oxide ring. The mass fragmentation pattern of the triacetate is typical of Δ^{12} -oleanene skeleton.

Careyagenol B (16-desoxy barringtogenol C) :

Careyagenol B (Va), C₃₀H₅₀O₄, m.p. 291°-92°, [α]_D²⁵ +58.7 (EtOH) formed a tetraacetate (Vb), C₃₆H₅₈O₈, m.p. 223°-24°, [α]_D²⁵ +46.5 (CHCl₃). This compound was found to be identical (m.p., mixed m.p., TLC) with 16 desoxy barringtogenol C recently isolated as a minor saponin of Japanese Horse chestnut by Kitagawa *et al*^{20,14}. Mention may be made of a few new derivatives which were prepared in connection with the identification of the compound. The tetraacetate (Vb) on heating with SeO₂ in glacial acetic acid under reflux afforded a *trans* heteroannular diene (VI) characteristic of Δ^{12} -oleanenes. The tetrol (Va) consumed one m mole of periodic acid which is consistent with the presence of a α -glycol system. Moreover, the compound (Va) formed only a mono acetonide (VII) involving C₂₂ and C₂₃ hydroxyls. This confirmed the *trans* orientation of the α -glycol system at C₂₁ and C₂₂. The mass spectrum of the tetraacetate (Vb) is compatible with its structure. It did not show the molecular ion peak at m/e 642 but showed the (M-60) peak at m/e 582 (100%) due to facile loss of a molecule of acetic acid in the ionizing chamber, a phenomenon of common occurrence.

The NMR spectrum of the tetraacetate (Vb) shows down field signals at δ 5.42 (C₁₂-H, m), 4.60 (C₃- α H, *t*-like), 5.0 (d, J = 11 Hz) and 5.39 (d, J = 11 Hz) (two *trans* diaxial H at C₂₁ and C₂₂), 2.04 (3H, -OCOCH₃, s), 2.11 (3H, -OCOCH₃, s), 2.12 (6H, 2x-OCOCH₃, s) and 3.85 (C₁₇-CH₂OAc, s). The tertiary methyls appear as sharp singlets at δ 0.91 (9H, s), 0.97 (3H, s), 1.01 (3H, s), 1.08 (3H, s) and 1.26 (3H, s).

fragment a, m/e 249

fragment b, m/e 390

Careyagenol A (Barringtogenol C) :

The presence of barringtogenol D as well as careyagenol D which are actually artifacts of barringtogenol C (VIII)²¹ suggested the possibility of the presence of barringtogenol C in the seeds. In fact Careyagenol A, C₃₀H₅₀O₅, m.p. 308°–10°, [α]_D²⁵ +43.7° (EtOH), amorphous pentaacetate, m.p. 143°–46°, tetraacetate, m.p. 222°–24° was eventually found to be identical with barringtogenol C²¹ (m.p., m.m.p., TLC, IR).

Experimental

Petroleum used had b.p. 60°–80°, m.p.s. are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded as Nujol mulls. NMR spectra were obtained with CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal standard.

Extraction procedure :

Powdered seeds (1.02 kg) of *Careya arborea* Roxb. was extracted successively with petroleum, chloroform and ethanol. The ethanolic extract on removal of the solvent yielded the crude saponin as dark brown powder (72 g) which was hydrolysed with 5% ethanolic hydrochloric acid (480 ml) at reflux for 16 hr. Alcohol was evaporated off on water bath keeping the volume same on frequent addition of water. It was then filtered and the residue was washed with water until free from acid. The residue was dried and the dried residue (41.5 g) was chromatographed on a column of neutral Brochmann alumina (1 kg), elution being carried out successively with benzene, benzene-ether mixture (1 : 1), ether and ether-methanol mixture (1 : 1). Thus four fractions were separated: fraction 1 (eluted with benzene) (11.2 g), fraction 2 (eluted with benzene-ether mixture) (4.2 g), fraction 3 (eluted with ether) (1.4 g) and fraction 4 (eluted with ether-methanol mixture) (3.6 g).

Fraction 1 was a gummy material and no crystalline matter could be obtained from it.

Fraction 2 was rechromatographed on alumina (150 g) and the fractions were again divided into two fractions, an early fraction (A) (350 mg) and the later fraction (B) (3.2 g) using benzene-ether mixture (1 : 1) as eluent.

Isolation of careyagenol D (Ia) :

Fraction (A) (350 mg) was acetylated with acetic anhydride (10 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) on water bath for 1 hr. The product on chromatographic purification followed by crystallization from MeOH-CHCl₃

afforded careyagenol D tetraacetate (Ib) in long needles (260 mg), m.p. 282°–83°, [α]_D²⁵ –8° (CHCl₃); IR 1740, 1242 (acetate carbonyl), 838 trisubstituted double bond, 960 (disubstituted double bond) and 1380 cm⁻¹ (C-Me), mass m/e 640 (M⁺, 1.2), 580 (M⁺-AcOH, 8.6), 520 (M⁺-2AcOH, 2), 460 (M⁺-3AcOH, 1.2), 447 (M⁺-2AcOH-CH₂OAc, 6.8), 405 (M⁺-2AcOH-CH₂OAc-C₂H₂O, 8.6), 390 (fragment b, 26), 330 (b-AcOH, 4), 270 (b-2AcOH, 17.4), 257 (b-AcOH-CH₂OAc, 48), 215 (b-AcOH-CH₂OAc-C₂H₂O, 100), 197 (b-2AcOH-CH₂OAc, 87), 249 (fragment a, 74), 189 (a-AcOH, 52%). (Found : C, 71.21; H, 8.71; C₃₈H₅₆O₈ requires : C, 71.22; H, 8.81%).

Careyagenol D tetraacetate (Ib) (150 mg) was refluxed with 5% ethanolic KOH (15 ml) for 2 hr. Working up in the usual way and crystallization from EtOH Careyagenol D (Ia) was obtained as micro needles (130 mg), m.p. 301°–2°, [α]_D²⁵ +15.5 (EtOH). (Found : C, 76.26; H, 9.96; C₃₀H₄₈O₄ requires : C, 76.23; H, 10.24%).

Preparation of the α, β-unsaturated ketone (IV) :

The tetraacetate (Ib) (50 mg) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was heated to reflux and then CrO₃ (50 mg) in acetic acid (85%, 5 ml) was added gradually over a period of 1 hr. Refluxing was continued for another hour and then diluted with water. The precipitate was filtered, purified by chromatography and crystallised from MeOH as colourless needles m.p. 273°–74°, UV (EtOH), 238 nm (log ε 4.11) IR, 1678 cm⁻¹ (α, β-unsaturated ketone) (Found : C, 69.64; H, 8.29; C₃₈H₅₄O₉ requires : C, 69.70; H, 8.31%).

Preparation of the Acetonide Derivatives of (Ia) :

To a solution of careyagenol D (Ia) (100 mg) in dioxane-acetone mixture (1 : 2) (20 ml) was added 5 drops of conc. HCl and left overnight. It was poured into cold water and the product was worked up in the usual manner. The preparative TLC separation of the mixture of acetonides (35 mg) using Silica Gel G, and CHCl₃ furnished a major acetonide (21 mg) and a minor one (10 mg). The major acetonide (probably involving C₂₁ and C₂₂ hydroxyls) on crystallization from ether-*n*-hexane yielded colourless crystals m.p. 244°–46°. (Found : C, 77.23; H 10.18; C₃₃H₅₂O₄ requires : C, 77.29; H, 10.22%). The minor acetonide (probably involving C₂₂ and C₂₃ hydroxyls) also on crystallization from ether-*n*-hexane yielded colourless crystals, m.p. 235°–37°. (Found : C, 77.26; H, 10.17; C₃₃H₅₂O₄ requires : C, 77.29; H, 10.22%).

Periodic acid oxidation of careyagenol D :

Careyagenol D (60 mg) was dissolved in methanol (20 ml). 5 ml of 0.5 M periodic acid aq. was added and left for 20 hr. A blank experiment was performed side by side. Excess of periodic acid was titrated with standard sodium arsenite soln. Consumption of periodic acid per mole of the compound was found to be one mole.

Isolation of barringtogenol D :

Fraction (B) (2.5 g) on acetylation with acetic anhydride (25 ml) and pyridine (2 ml) in the usual way and chromatographic purification of the product followed by crystallization from MeOH-CHCl₃ afforded barringtogenol D triacetate (IIb) as needles (2.89 g), m.p. 237°-38°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 78^\circ$ (CHCl₃); IR 1740, 1240 (acetate carbonyl), 1150 (ether linkage), 838 (trisubstituted double bond) and 1380 cm⁻¹ (C-Me). (Found : C, 72.61; H, 9.40; Calc. for C₃₆H₅₄O₇ : C, 72.21; H, 9.09%).

Barringtogenol D triacetate (IIb) (200 mg) was refluxed with 5% ethanolic KOH (25 ml) for 2 hr. This after working up in the usual way and recrystallization from MeOH-EtOH afforded barringtogenol D (IIa) as needles (170 mg), m.p. 308°-10°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 20.4^\circ$ (EtOH) (Found : C, 76.90; H, 9.96; Calc. for C₃₀H₄₈O₄ : C, 76.23; H, 10.24%).

Preparation of the Diketomethyl ester from barringtogenol D :

To a suspension of barringtogenol D (600 mg) in acetone (50 ml) was added gradually Jones¹⁹ oxidation mixture until orange brown colour persisted. The mixture was worked up in the usual way and the acid obtained was esterified with diazomethane. The ester (290 mg) was chromatographed on acid washed alumina. The petroleum ether eluate on crystallization from *n*-hexane afforded the diketomethylester as long needles, m.p. 220°-21° (Found : C, 74.85; H, 9.07; Calc. for C₃₁H₄₄O₅ : C, 74.96; H, 8.93%).

Conversion of barringtogenol D triacetate to Careyagenol D tetraacetate :

Following the method of Barua *et al*¹ barringtogenol D triacetate (150 mg) was boiled with acetic anhydride and to this boiling soln. was added *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (80 mg) gradually over a period of 20 min. The mixture was then refluxed for another hr. and left at room temperature overnight. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way and the product obtained was chromatographed on alumina and finally crystallised from MeOH-CHCl₃ mixture as needles (50 mg), m.p. 281°-82°. This was found to be identical with careyagenol D tetraacetate obtained from the acid hydrolyzate of the seed saponin.

Isolation of 16-desoxy barringtogenol C (Va) :

Fraction 2 (1.5 g) on acetylation with acetic anhydride (20 ml) and pyridine (1.5 ml) at 140° for 1 hr. and chromatographic purification of the product followed by crystallization from MeOH afforded

16-desoxy barringtogenol C tetraacetate (Vb) as needles (1.01 g), m.p. 223°-24°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 46.5^\circ$ (CHCl₃), IR 1740, 1240 (acetate carbonyl) 838 (trisubstituted double bond) and 1380 cm⁻¹ (C-Me), mass m/e 580 (M⁺ - CH₃COOH, 100), 522 (M⁺ - 2 × CH₃COOH, 37), 462 (M⁺ - 3 × CH₃COOH, 16), 449 (M⁺ - 2 × CH₃COOH - CH₂OCOCH₃, 12), 332 (ion *b* - CH₃COOH, 45), 272 (*b* - 2 × CH₃COOH, 33.3), 230 (*b* - 2 × CH₃COOH - C₂H₅O, 24), 212 (*b* - 3 × CH₃COOH, 57), 199 (*b* - 2 × CH₃COOH - CH₂OCOCH₃, 53), 249 (ion *a*, 26.7), 190 (*a* - CH₃COOH + H, 60) and 189 (*a* - CH₃COOH, 46.6%). (Found : C, 70.62; H, 9.04; Calc. for C₃₈H₅₈O₈ : C, 71.00; H, 9.09%).

The tetraacetate (500 mg) was refluxed with 5% ethanolic KOH (40 ml) for 2 hr. This after recrystallization from MeOH-EtOH afforded 16-desoxy barringtogenol C as needles, m.p. 291°-92°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 58.7^\circ$ (EtOH) (Found : C, 75.84; H, 10.31; Calc. for C₃₀H₅₀O₄ : C, 75.90; H, 10.62%).

SeO₂ oxidation of 16-desoxy barringtogenol C tetraacetate :

The tetraacetate (Vb) (100 mg) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed with freshly sublimed SeO₂ (100 mg) for 4 hr. The soln. was filtered hot and the filtrate was diluted with water and worked up in the usual way. The crude product was chromatographed on alumina and the petrol-benzene (1:4) eluate on crystallization from methanol afforded the diene (VI) m.p. 226°-27°, UV (EtOH), 240, 247 and 257 nm (log ϵ 4.42, 4.46 and 4.36) (Found : C, 71.20; H, 8.78; C₃₈H₅₆O₈ requires : C, 71.22; H, 8.81%).

Periodic acid oxidation of 16-desoxy barringtogenol C :

16-desoxy barringtogenol C (75 mg) in methanol (30 ml) was treated with 7 ml. of 0.5 M periodic acid aq. and left for 20 hr. Excess of periodic acid was titrated with sodium arsenite soln. Consumption of periodic acid per mole of the compound was found to be one mole.

Preparation of the acetonide of (Va) :

To a soln. of 16-desoxy barringtogenol C (Va) (100 mg) in dioxane acetone mixture (1:2) (20 ml) was added 5 drops of conc. HCl and left overnight. The product was worked up in the usual way and the acetonide was crystallised from ether *n*-hexane, m.p. 248°-50° (Found : C, 76.88; H, 10.46; C₃₃H₅₄O₄ requires : C, 77.00; H, 10.57%).

Isolation of barringtogenol C (VIII) :

Fraction 4 (3.6 g) on acetylation with acetic anhydride (30 ml) and pyridine (2.5 ml) at reflux and separation of the mixture of acetates by chromatography afforded a amorphous pentaacetate (560 mg) m.p. 143°-46° and a tetraacetate which could be crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 222°-24°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 16.5^\circ$ (CHCl₃). Both the tetraacetate and the pentaacetate on saponification with 5% ethanolic KOH in the usual way afforded barringtogenol C, m.p. 308°-10°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 43.7^\circ$ (EtOH). (Found : C, 73.36; H, 10.24; Calc. for C₃₀H₅₀O₅ : C, 73.43; H, 10.27%).

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